

RISK ANALYSIS

IN

PROJECT MANAGEMENT

BY

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Abstract

No matter how well you plan your project, there is the probability you can always run into unexpected problems, hence managing risk is nothing more than identifying risks, it involves providing necessary risk analysis and risk response. Managing risk is an important function in making the project successful, every company is initially responsible for all project related risks as the company decides whether to execute projects or not. Project risks must be proactively managed throughout the project lifecycle.

This paper discusses various methodologies that shows the importance of how risk analysis is an effective tool in risk management.

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Introduction

According to PMBOK Guild, “project risk management is the systematic process of identifying, analyzing and responding to project risk. It includes maximizing the probability and consequences of positive events and minimizing the probability and consequences of adverse effects to project objectives. (Project Management Institute 2018)

Project risk is an uncertain event or condition that, if it occurs, has a positive or negative effect on at least one of the project objectives, if these risks are not managed proactively using a structured approach, then they can result in serious consequences for the project. (Doloi 2013)

The objectives of project risk management are to increase the probability and impact of positive events and decrease the probability and impact of negative events in the project. When project risk occurred, it has a positive or a negative effect on the project objectives, project objectives include scope, schedule, cost, and quality. (Doloi 2013)

It is imperative for us to be proactive in our risk management, as negligence can lead to dire consequences for our projects, hence the need for project risk management. Project risk management aims to identify and prioritize risk in advance of their occurrence and provide action-oriented information to project managers. This orientation requires consideration of events that may or may not occur and are therefore describe in teams of likelihood or probability of occurrence in addition to other dimensions such as their impact on objectives.

Literature Review

In general risk management process helps identify all items that can impact a project for both cost and schedule.

Here are risk related definitions from AACE International recommended practice RP 10S-90 (AACE, Recommended Practice No. 10S - 90 2016):

Risk: An uncertain future event that, if it occurs, will affect project objectives either positively (upside) or negatively (downside); resulting in outcome of uncertainty

Issue: Actual problem that can affect objectives if not managed (potential for loss)

Uncertainty: An unknown event due to inherent lack of knowledge or ambiguity (i.e., weather, subsurface, etc.)

Threat: An unfavorable condition or situation that can lead to a risk (i.e., issue, uncertainty, etc.)

Opportunity: Potential for gain (favorable condition or situation, good idea, or response)

Impact (Severity, Risk Exposure): Effect of the risk if it occurs, on project objectives

Probability: Likelihood of occurrence of risk, measured in percentage

The four attributes of project management are - Plan, Organize, Direct, and Control. These management concepts, allow any company, to handle the tactical, planned and set decisions. In addition, these functions are adequate to enable the company with a controlled plan over the preventative measures to maintain the project within established cost and schedule. (Lee 2015)

DISCUSSION

In our everyday activities, we are exposed to risks, somehow, we are able to manage with some level of success, by unknowingly taking risk in our daily chores. On any project, the project manager must act responsibly on behalf of all stakeholders, and other affected parties. It should be noted that risk management process would increase the project budget for handling risks.

The risk process relies heavily on the judgments and experience of the project manager, the project team or person that will handle the risk process. It also relies on historical data from the company database of similar projects they had done in the past.

The processes identified in the project management body of knowledge (PMBOK) will support any risk management concept for all disciplines. Six major processes are as follows (Hyde 2010):

1. Risk management planning
2. Risk identification
3. Qualitative risk analysis
4. Quantitative risk analysis
5. Risk response planning
6. Risk monitoring and control

In order to implement effective cost controls or effective schedule controls, risk management process should be based on industry best practices. The following, best practices currently in use are as follows (Hyde 2010):

- Create an integrated project controls system
- Develop an accurate cost estimate
- Establish a comprehensive project budget
- Develop an integrated schedule baseline
- Develop an effective risk management plan
- Implement an earned value management system
- Conduct independent reviews and audits of cost, schedule and risks
- Reduce change orders and keep costs and schedule in control

Risk Sources

Before listing typical sources for project related risks, let us define the differences between risk and issue. An issue is something that can be resolved. On the other hand, risk reflects uncertainty and will require mitigation to resolve. Depending on the procedures adopted by the company, based on actual circumstances, managing risks and issues together makes sense. For example, in projects managing and reporting risks and issues together makes sense as they both can affect the outcome of the project. (Dan 2012)

Risk sources can be subdivided into the following groups, based on the underlying source. However, certain events or conditions highlighted during risk identification session, might affect the outcome of a project. (Dan 2012)

Risk Categories

Risk management is an important activity of project management. So, it is important to classify risks appropriately:

1. Technical risks: These are risks associated with project development for items like scope of work, detailed design, construction and operation of facilities and processes. In addition, it may affect the functional and operational requirements of the project. (Uppal 2013)
2. Cost risk: This is associated with the capability of the project team to achieve the established project life-cycle costs. This includes cost for items like detailed design, construction, and operations. In addition, it will address the accuracy of the overall cost estimate. Cost risk is quite simply the uncertainty about the project estimated costs. Some cost risks may affect the schedule, task duration uncertainty etc., but others are totally independent of schedule. (Uppal 2013)
3. Schedule risk: This is associated with allocating adequate amount of time for each activity in project planning, for activities like - regulatory approval, detailed design, construction, startup, operations, and other similar activities. (Uppal 2013)
4. Budget Risk: This is the result of establishing wrong budget estimate for the project. In addition, project scope creep will add additional cost to the budget, resulting in additional project cost risk. This risk may result in further delay of project completion or at times even an incomplete termination of the project (Uppal 2013)

5. Business Risk: If the project gets delayed due to late management approval, it may result in losing the market share and may make the project unprofitable. Furthermore, any delay in receiving timely inputs from the customer or other business entities may result in additional business risks. (Uppal 2013)

6. Infrastructure Risk: This is the result of poor planning of all activities associated with infrastructure. In order to avoid project delays, it is essential to assign adequate resources during project activities like detailed design, construction and start-up. It is essential to do proper planning of infrastructure for maintaining the project schedule. (Uppal 2013)

7. Operational Risk: This is the result of improper execution of process related events. This risk can occur for not assigning adequate resources during start-up. (Uppal 2013)

8. Resource Risk: This is the result of improper management of factors like - staff availability, project budget, overall schedule and use of facilities. (Uppal 2013)

9. Supplier Risk is the result of some third-party supplier assigned with developing the project. This risk occurs when the capabilities of the supplier are inadequate. (Uppal 2013)

A risk breakdown structure, or RBS for short, is a hierarchical chart that breaks down project risks starting with higher-level categories and continuing down into sub-levels of risk.

Figure 1 — Risk Breakdown Structure (Jennifer Greens 2016)

Key Elements of Risk Management Plan

Project risk management plan requires a set of deliverables for each phase of the project life cycle.

The key deliverables for all phases are: (Uppal 2013)

- a. A risk register with all identified risks; their owners; pre- and post-mitigation assessments for each risk; their response strategy and action plans if required.
- b. A Risk Management Plan that documents:
 - The ongoing process of identification, review and (re)assessment of risks relative to project objectives.
 - Roles and responsibilities that enable risk management.
 - How to manage risks.

- Based on project management and project team requirements, a predetermined review cycle is a necessity for timely reporting and communicating of risks.

The overall risk management planning process (AACE, Recommended Practice No.72R - 12 n.d.) as per AACE International recommended Practice RP 72R-12 is shown below.

Figure 2 — Process for Developing, Implementing and Maintaining a Risk Management Plan

Planning for Risk Identification

The process of identifying and capturing risks or opportunities could be started only after establishing basic project information and the established goals for the project. Furthermore, all team members should be aware all the risk categories are to be considered for identifying project related risks. In addition to the project team, a designated facilitator should be appointed to start this process for capturing risks. As a rule, all risk sessions should be conducted with active participation of all team members and other personnel that could be invited to risk sessions. (AACE, Recommended Practice No.62R - 11 2011)

A well facilitated risk identification session with the project team helps in achieving these communication goals, effective Risk Management requires (Fortunato 2012):

- A structured, continuous process to identify risks
- An agreed set of Probabilities & Consequence scales (RAM) to assess risks

- A supporting organizational framework to manage risks

Risk Workshop Overview and Objectives for Project Team (Nilsen 2018):

- Continuously identify new risks and opportunities
- Accurately describe & properly assess risks according to the Project RAM
- Create and implement action plans to minimize impact of potential risks
- Communicate risks and action plans to those who need to know
- Monitor and appraise effectiveness of action plans
- Monitor and modify likelihood and severity of risk
- Update of Risk & Action status by Risk Owner
- Update of Risk information in risk register by Risk Owner

The Risk Register is a tool in risk management and project management, it is used to documents the assessments, response plans, and progress. The Risk Register is the record of all project risks identified, assessed, and managed by the risk management process.

The Risk Register should contain (Uppal 2013):

- Risks (not issues or uncertainties) assessed against appropriate consequences
- Risks from a wide variety of sources.
- Opportunities as well as Threats.

The Purpose of the Risk Register is to (Uppal 2013):

- Provide on demand access, for all interested/affected parties to the latest official register of risks to project objectives.
- Document the interrelation between individual risks (association, causality)
- Provide an evergreen record of changes over time (progress tracking / audit trail)
- Provide a picture of the distribution of risks by Consequence.

A risk should be identified and assessed initially taking into account the effects of normal work processes to reduce the likelihood of occurrence, or the level of consequence, or both. The resulting pre-mitigated (gross) severity should be tested against the project risk acceptance threshold, and if unacceptable, response plans should be devised, and the risk would be reassessed to determine if

the post-mitigated (residual) severity is acceptable. Responses may have to be enhanced or the strategy modified, based on the judgement and effectiveness of the responses (Curran 2000).

Risk ID	Identified risk	Potential response	Root cause	Category	Priority	Urgency
R-01	Landslide caused by loose gravel and dirt on the nearby mountain	Put up barrier or dig trench	Geological data review found loose topsoil nearby	Natural	Low	Medium
R-02	High winds can lead to cliff disaster	Reinforce tent stakes; obtain weatherproof equipment	National Weather Service predicts 35% chance of high winds	Natural	High	Low
R-03	Storms predicted through the first two weeks of project schedule time	Create reserves to account for time lost due to storms	El Niño weather pattern	Natural	Medium	Low
R-04	If someone gets sick, it could be a problem getting medical care	Bring a doctor with us on the project	Nearest hospital is 50 miles away	Human	Low	Low

Table 1 — Example of a Typical Risk Register (Jennifer Greens 2016)

Risk Management has to be the responsibility of all project team members. If a project does not have a dedicated risk coordinator, the roles and responsibilities shown below under the risk coordinator should be allocated to team management or team members as appropriate (Uppal 2013).

Project Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Champions the risk management process • Approves risk responses and assigns resources for the risks • Escalates risks beyond his authority to upper management • Uses the risk information for evaluating options and preparing decisions
Risk Coordinator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drafts the Risk Management Plan for Project Manager • Trains and supports risk owners and project team members • Maintains the risk register: • Screens proposed risks and accepts/rejects into risk register
Risk Owner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describes and assesses the risk and proposes appropriate risk responses • Obtains approval and resources (Action Owners) for planned responses • Tracks progress, reviews risk and closes risks • Keeps continuous record of risk status in risk register
Action Owner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Executes actions as agreed with risk owner • Records action status in risk register
Team Member	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifies risks and proposes them to the risk register • Feeds back effectiveness of risk responses to risk owner • Is aware of top project risks and risks impacting his own work

Table 2 — Roles and Responsibilities

Project team members should be expected to identify risks in the course of their normal day-to-day work or during dedicated risk events, such as regularly scheduled risk management workshops. Risks could be identified through techniques such as, brainstorming, document reviews, interviews, Delphi technique and SWOT Analysis. Additional identification methods may be via check lists, assumption analysis and diagramming techniques. Here are the five techniques more common in the industry for identifying risks.

Techniques for Identifying Risks (AACE, Recommended Practice No.62R - 11 2011):

Brainstorming: This method revolves around building consensus, based on views of every team member. Brainstorming is one of the most effective methods for capturing risks.

Document reviews: This involves references to documents of previous projects and their identified risks from their risk registers. Risk records lead to a better understanding of possible hurdles that will arise in the project.

Delphi technique: This is a brainstorming method except that members are anonymous to each other.

Interviewing: It is always helpful when there are experts on the team or team members who were part of previous projects. This process will help capture all project risks.

SWOT Analysis: This method revolves around assessing businesses and projects strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, threats, and ways to work around these aspects.

The risk owner ensures that the planned responses have the desired effect by assessing the as-mitigated severity. In addition, the risk owner ensures that the proposed risk responses are specific, measurable, actionable, realistic, and time based. Each action must be assigned a planned start date and a planned finish date in the risk register, which should be selected relative to the expected risk occurrence date. The Risk Owner can assign an action owner to execute the planned responses and follows their progress. Completion of the actions should be required prior to the action finish date. (AACE, Recommended Practice No.72R - 12 n.d.)

However, every risk owner is responsible for regularly reviewing the progress of all their risks to verify if:

- The risk needs to be re-assessed due to changes in the risk landscape.
- The risk response strategy is still appropriate or needs to be changed.
- Response planning and implementation are progressing on schedule, and any schedule changes should be reflected in the response planning.

Qualitative Risk Analysis

Qualitative risk analysis is the process of assessing the impact and the likelihood of identified risk. This process prioritizes risks according to their potential effects on project objectives. It is not enough to know the risks on the project, some of the risks identified are likely to occur, while others are very improbable. It is the ones that is most likely to happen we plan for. Besides, some risks will cause a whole lot of damage to the project if they happen, while others will barely make a scratch, hence we care much more about the risks that will have a big impact, that is why we need to perform risk assessment to know the likelihood and impact of the risk on our project

Quantitative Risk Analysis

The quantitative risk analysis process aims to analyze numerically the probability of each risk and its consequences on project objectives, as well as the extent of the overall project risk. This process uses techniques such as Monte Carlo simulation and decision analysis. (Project Management Institute 2018)

Once risks have been identified and ranked according to the team's assessment, there is need to take the analysis a little further and back it up my numbers. Sometimes the initial assessment needs to be updated when you look into it further.

Risk Response Planning

Risk response planning is the process of developing options and determining actions to enhance opportunities and reduce treats to the project objectives. It includes the identification and assignment of individuals or parties to take responsibility for each agreed risk response. This process ensures that identified risks are properly address

Functions of Management

In general, every company has developed and implemented their own project management concepts for the purpose of executing projects. These concepts help them achieve the objectives of every project on a consistent basis. The four basic functions of management are Plan, Organize, Direct and Control. However, planning is the core area of management. Planning is ongoing, and it forces the company management to assess; where the company is at present, and where it will be in the future. Based on these assessments an appropriate course of action could be implemented to achieve company goals and objectives.

Important success factors for realizing successful projects are:

- Acceptance by the company
- Meeting all expectations
- Meeting all project milestones or deadlines
- Sponsor’s involvement and ownership
- Meeting overall project budget
- Meeting quality criteria
- Managing scope creep
- Professional risk and issue management
- Excellent project management

Figure 3 — Project Controls Workflow during Project Phases (McMullen 2016)

Conclusion

Project managers and all those involved in the project should always work to identify risks across the project. There should be a holistic approach to the process of risk identification, analysis, response, monitoring and provision of feedbacks to decision-makers for their inputs. There should be an integrated project control system to managed risks that might affect the outcome of the project. Most attention should be given to the highest-priority risk factors identified during the risk session. Risk monitoring and control will help the company to determine whether to execute the project and accept all the risks as recorded in the risk register or terminate the project.

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